

Staffing as a topical issue of the modern fitness industry

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The article substantiates the problem of staffing the fitness industry of Ukraine.

Purpose: to study the current state of the problem of staffing in the system of health fitness in Ukraine.

Material & Methods: theoretical analysis and synthesis of scientific literature, sources and information of the world Internet, comparison and comparison method, system analysis, organizational analysis, expert evaluation.

Results: in recent years have increased the attention of scientists to personnel issues in the field of physical culture and sports, in particular – fitness. The strengthening of the social significance of the professional activities of fitness industry professionals is due to new socio-economic changes, the development of our state in accordance with the new market conditions. The processes of transformation, globalization and integration that are currently taking place in the system of health fitness in Ukraine require the improvement of its staffing. The necessity of providing the labor market with competitive specialists has been proved, since in the professional environment there is a shortage of qualified fitness personnel and a mismatch of competencies in a large part of the existing personnel with modern challenges.

Conclusions: the need for scientific substantiation of the concept of staffing in the system of health fitness in Ukraine has been actualized in order to overcome the revealed contradictions between existing practice and the requirements of modernity.

Keyword: fitness, staffing, fitness industry, professional standards, competence.

Introduction

The problem of formation and further effective use of personnel potential was considered and considered in the scientific works of both foreign and domestic scientists. Among them are the following: E. Mayo, M. Meskon, D. Sule, F. Taylor, A. Fayol, V. Dyatlov, A. Egorshin, P. Zhuravlev, A. Kibanova, E. Maslov, Yu. Odegov, V. Travin, S. Shekshnya, G. Shchekin and others. Since each sphere has its own characteristics of functioning, staffing the fitness industry requires study and research, because there are many debatable and unresolved problems in this direction.

The field of physical culture and sports provides physical fitness services to various segments of the population. The growing demand of the population for health promotion, physical improvement and active recreation contributed to the development of the fitness industry in Ukraine, which is a relatively new business area. Today it is one of the most dynamic segments of the sphere of physical culture and sports, which is developing [25]. Competition in the modern market, a wide range of fitness services puts quite high demands on staffing [7; 8]. The effectiveness of the work of fitness clubs, their success in achieving certain goals depends on the quality of staff. That is why in modern conditions the fitness industry needs specialists who have received appropriate training and ensure their further professional growth in order to properly compete in the labor market and meet the new needs of consumers of their services.

Purpose of the study: to study the current state of the prob-

lem of staffing in the system of health fitness in Ukraine.

Material and Methods of the research

Research methods: theoretical analysis and synthesis of scientific literature, sources and information of the world Internet, comparison and collation method.

Results of the research

Today, mainly, training and retraining of personnel in the field of physical culture and sports is provided by the state (the law of Ukraine "On physical culture and sports"). The dynamic development of the fitness industry necessitates the need for qualified personnel. That is why there is a need to implement measures to improve the system of staffing in the sphere of recreational fitness, which would satisfy the requirements of the fitness industry.

In the National Report "The Sustainable Development Goals of Ukraine", the Government presented 17 sustainable development goals adapted for Ukraine (2015–2030) [41]. Among the main ones are defined "good health and well-being" (goal 3), the achievement of which should be the main concern of society and "quality education" (goal 4). The government sees their achievements as possible due to the reform of both the health system and the education system in Ukraine [41]. All this leads to increased scientific interest in the study of the phenomenon of public-private partnership [22] in these areas, in particular – in physical culture and sports. Today, em-

ployers do not sufficiently trust the state of training and offer their own training programs (non-formal education) to form professional competencies [7]. The field of activity of specialists in recreational fitness provides professional readiness for teaching, research, advisory, cultural, educational, coaching, organizational, managerial and other activities in the system of special education and the fitness industry in accordance with established requirements. That is why, in our opinion, at the present stage, the main tasks of improving the system of personnel support for the functioning of the sphere are the development of requirements for the qualifications of employees, their competencies, educational qualification characteristics (professions: fitness trainer, aerobics instructor, etc.), which they serve as the basis for the professional standard (the formation of professional qualifications) and the industry standard for higher education in the relevant specialty. It is the professional standard that will allow to determine general and labor functions, qualification level, actions, performed by employees within their professional sphere, as well as the necessary knowledge and skills.

field of physical culture and sports: the Constitution of Ukraine and the laws of Ukraine "On Education", "On Higher Education", "On Physical Culture and Sport", Concept of the State Program "Health 2020: Ukrainian dimension" for 2012–2020 (2011), National strategy for improving motor activity in Ukraine for the period up to 2025 "Motor activity – a healthy lifestyle – a healthy nation" (2016), Action Plan for the implementation of the National Qualifications Framework of Ukraine for 2016–2020 and the like.

The system analysis of published materials suggests that in recent years, both domestic and foreign scientists have increased their attention to personnel issues in the field of physical culture and sports (Table 1).

Most of the conducted research concerns the training of future specialists:

- on physical education and sports (Sushchenko L.P.)
- with adaptive physical education (G. Karpyuk)
- on physical recreation (Andreeva A.V., Krutsevich T.Yu.)
- using an interdisciplinary approach (S. Balandin I.)
- managers in physical culture and sports (Sazonov I.Yu., Lomovtseva O.V., Kuzmin A.M.)
- in recreational and recreational activities (Danilevich M.V.)
- to the introduction of health fitness technologies in the school (A. Atamas);
- to improve their quality (Bondin V.I., Putilina T.A.)
- to conduct lessons (fitness classes) with different age groups (Saikina E.G., Batischeva M.G., Krendeleva V.V.)
- on the use of health fitness technologies (Zakharina E.A.)
- on competitiveness (Khazova S.A.), etc.

Investigating the issue of staffing the fitness industry, we also relied on the development of domestic and foreign scientists, who examined various aspects of it in their research (Table 2).

These scientific works cover a wide range of issues of staffing the fitness industry, in particular, the professional activity of a fitness trainer. Thus, experts [5; 7; 32] highlighted the current state of training of specialists who will work in the fitness industry, in institutions of higher education (universities). The absence of professional higher education in most fitness trainers was stated. The prices and the introduction of health

Table 1
Study of the problems of staffing in the field of physical culture and sports

No.	Meaning of the problem	Authors
1.	Theoretical foundations of professional training of specialists in the field of physical culture and sports	Karpyuk R.P., 2008; Hazova S.A., 2011; Matrosova O.Yu., 2011; Sushchenko L.P., 2003, 2015, 2017; Azhippo O.Yu., 2013; Zakharina Ye.A., 2013; Belikova N.O., 2012, 2017; Andreeva O.V., Blagoy O.L., 2015; Atamas O.A., 2015; Sushchenko V.P., 2016; Stepanchenko N.I., 2017; Kuznetsov N.I., 2017; Bondin V.I., Putilina T.A., 2017; Danilevich M.V., 2018; Sazonov I.Yu., Lomovtseva O.V. and others, 2018
2.	Personnel support of physical culture and sports in Ukraine, training for: - social sphere; - sports of the highest achievements	Gasiuk I.L., 2010; Kulish N.M., 2016; Dutchak M., Shkrebtiy Yu. et al., 2010
3.	Mechanisms of state management of the development of physical culture i sport in higher educational institutions of Ukraine	Vavrenyuk S.A., 2015
4.	Conceptual bases of professional training of specialists in physical education and sport	Kurilo V.S., 2006
5.	Functioning and development of physical culture and sports in the market	Michuda Yu.P, 2008
6.	Place and value of vocational guidance in the process of staffing the field of physical culture and sports	Zolotukhina I., 2007
7.	Problems of state personnel policy in the field of physical culture and sports	Oluiko V. M., 2006; Moiseyeva S., 2012; Zhurba M.A., 2017; Melnichenko O.A., 2016
8.	Internal resource development in the field of physical culture and sports	Leonov Ya.V., Prikhodko I.I. and others, 2013

fitness in schools of various types: pre-school institutions, secondary schools, universities, etc. [28; 32]. That is, there is a certain social demand for relevant specialists, to which the education system would respond promptly and adequately. In Ukraine, the formation of a system of training specialists for the sphere of health fitness continues.

Our analysis of the scientific literature suggests that the considerable attention of domestic scientists to the problems of training future fitness trainers in higher educational institutions. M. Vasilenko [8] thoroughly covers her in her works [8]. A. A. Berest examines the preparation of future fitness trainers in recreational and recreational activities [4], A. K. Kornosenko – the specifics and functions of the professional activity of a fitness trainer [18], A. V. Korh-Cherba – the main directions

Table 2

Study of the problems of staffing of the fitness industry

No.	Meaning of the problem	Authors
1.	Fitness trainer training system	Levitsky V., 2005; Korh-Cherba O.V., 2015 [19]; Pristupa E., Muzika F., Zhdanova O., Chekhovska L., 2017 [32]; Vasilenko M.M., 2018 [7]
	Formation of professional competences of a fitness trainer	Volkov K.D., 2009 [9]; Milov Yu.V., Volf T.V., 2016 [26]; Slobozhaninov P.A., 2017 [35]
	Improving the professional competence of a fitness trainer	Levchenkova T.V. 2018 [24]
2.	Staffing of fitness in foreign countries	Levitsky V., 2011 [23]; Czerwiński J., 2001; Berezanskaya M., 2013 [3]; Vasilenko M.M., 2013 [6]; Zhdanova O., Chekhovskaya L., Shevtsev U, 2016 [16]
3.	Legal and regulatory aspects of the fitness trainer	Dutchak M., 2010 [13]; Dutchak M., Vasilenko M., 2013 [14]
4.	Staffing fitness clubs	Priimak M., 2016 [28]
5.	Advanced training of a fitness trainer, level of knowledge	Stacey D., Hopkins M., Adamo K.B., Shorr R., Prud'homme D., 2010 [52]; Priimak M., 2017 [29]
6.	Professional training: – trainer-teacher;	Svatyev A.V., 2013; Pavlyuk E.O. 2017
	– fitness trainer in Ukraine;	Miroshnikov A. B., Nesterov P.V., 2010 [27]; Berest O.O., 2015, 2016 [4; 5]; Pyatnitskaya D.V., 2016 [33]; Kornosenko O.K., 2015 [18]; Vasilenko M.M., 2018 [8];
	– fitness trainer in foreign countries	Vasilenko M.M., 2013 [6]; Saykyna E.G., 2015 [34]; Prima A., 2017 [30]; Tverdokhlib O., Kuzmenko N., Luscan O., 2010 [39];
	– athletic gymnastics instructor	Ponomarev V. O., 2010; SM Bulakh, 2015
7.	Technology management of physical education in organizations of fitness-oriented	Demekh S., Hayevy V., 2013 [12]
8.	Certification / licensing of a fitness trainer	Deana I. Melton, Jeffrey A. Katula, Karen M. Mustian, 2011 [52]; Halvorson R., 2009 [48]; Feito, Y., 2018 [47]; Shestakova E.V., 2017 [43]
9.	The role of fitness professionals and their impact on consumer health	Alexander T.C. De Lyon, Ross D. Neville, Kathleen M. Armour, 2016 [46]
10.	Features of the activities of fitness managers	Melton D.I., Dail T.K., Katula J.A., Mustian K.M., 2010 [50]; Stadnyk S., 2017 [37]
11.	Providing fitness trainers with fitness services, taking into account: - quality	Aronov G.E., 2008; Smirnov S.I., 2013 [36]; Dutchak M., Malkova D., 2017 [15]
	- emotional aspect (pleasure)	McGuire, A.M., Anderson, D.F., Trail, G., 2009 [49]
	- management aspect	Smirnov S.I., 2013 [36]; Kabanovskaya Ye.S., 2008; Krusevich T., las T., 2012 [20]
12.	The specifics and functions of the professional activity of a fitness trainer	Kornosenko O.K., 2017 [18]; Vasilenko M.M., 2018[8]
	Evaluation of a fitness trainer	Melton D., Dail T. K., Jeffrey A. Katula, Karen M. Mustian, 2011 [51]; Chiu W., Lee Y., Lin T., 2010 [45]
	The level of pedagogical skill fitness trainer	Bennie J.A., Wiesner G.H., van Uffelen J.G.Z., Harvey J.T., Biddle S.J.H., 2017 [44]; Aftimichuk O., 2012 [1];
	“Professional burnout”	Volosatov E.B., 2010 [10];
	Adaptation to physical stress	Kutuzov A.E., 2012 [21];
	staff motivation	Fedorenko, T.M., Avershina, Yu.S., 2016[40]
13.	Evaluation of the competitiveness of institutions of the fitness industry	Gaptar V.M., 2010 [11]; Stadnik SA, Sereda N.V., 2016 [38]; Prypatie E., Chekhovskaya L., 2018 [31]
14.	Management, marketing in the domestic market of sports and recreational services	Potapyuk I.P., 2013; Smirnova V., 2015; Cherdantseva I.G., Ibragimova L.S., Ibragimov E.Yu., 2018 [42]

for the implementation of the system approach in the professional activity of the future fitness trainer [19], D. V. Pyatnitskaya – analysis of the forms of organization of the educational process of future fitness trainers [33], A. Prima – implementation of the competence approach in the formation of professional competence of future fitness trainers to the professional activities Fitna with industry [30] and so on.

In particular, A. V. Korh-Cherba also notes that in the field of fitness and fitness, mainly those who have completed short-term instructor training courses work and do not meet modern requirements of the fitness industry due to their professional qualifications [19].

In his research, M. M. Vasilenko notes the need to provide the

labor market with competitive specialists, since the professional environment discusses the problem of the lack of qualified fitness trainers and the mismatch of the competencies of physical education personnel with the reality of practice. The author emphasizes the need and feasibility of specifying employers' requirements for future fitness trainers [7]. That is why, in our opinion, cooperation between teachers and business is necessary, which would be appropriate and would contribute to improving the system of training, the quality of fitness services and the competitiveness of fitness clubs in general.

We agree and support the view that the professionalism of a fitness trainer affects the consumer and his health [46]. That is why it is necessary to regularly evaluate its activities [50] and the level of skill [2; 50], because it is possible to "professional burnout" [10] of the above-mentioned specialists that can negatively affect the quality of fitness services.

Special attention should be paid to the work of foreign experts in evaluating the activities of a fitness trainer [50; 51] and its certification [47; 48; 50; 51]. These aspects are interrelated and are mandatory in the professional activity of a fitness trainer. Unfortunately, domestic scientists do not carry out similar studies, since these aspects are not sufficiently implemented in the practice of health fitness in Ukraine.

We agree with the opinion of J. Czerwiński (2001) that the effectiveness of a specialist's professional activity depends on the quality of his training, level of professional knowledge, abilities and skills of applying the knowledge gained in practice, the level of readiness to carry out professional activities in modern market conditions, as new directions of fitness

However, V. V. Kovalchuk notes that it is necessary not only to possess knowledge and skills that form the basis of the profession and determine qualifications, but also to be able to realize the acquired professional potential and creatively influence the development of the production situation [17]. We share this opinion and consider it important for our research.

It should be noted that in the fitness industry the time of production and consumption of the product coincide in time. In this regard, the service manufacturer is also its seller. Therefore, the success of fitness centers, image and reputation depend on the attitude of staff to consumers, their satisfaction [49], the ability to provide a fitness service, the quality of which should be evaluated [15]. It is obvious that its competitiveness will also depend on these aspects and the strengths of the internal environment of a fitness club [11; 31; 38]. In general, everything will help increase the number of consumers.

As a result of generalization of practical experience of staffing organizations of the fitness industry, as well as the ranking of factors influencing staffing, which create a balance between the need for personnel and their availability, it was found that according to the degree of influence of a group of factors are arranged in the following sequence: professional qualification – 82%; socio-economic – 74%; political and legal – 67%; scientific and technical – 63%; demographic – 59%; economic and geographical – 43%; natural biological – 39%; ideological and moral – 37%. The degree of consistency of experts is $W = 0,82$.

Organizational analysis of the personnel components of the

fitness industry in Ukraine, analysis of the results of the fitness industry market research conducted by FitnessConnectUA (2016), allowed to establish that the level of service (3%) and professionalism of trainers (3%) in the structure of consumer preferences take only 6 and 7 places, and as of 2017 – the professionalism of coaches (5%), and the level of service (4%) – 7 and 8 respectively. This indicates a lack of awareness among consumers of fitness services about the correlation between staffing and quality of services. It should be noted that the market of the fitness industry in Ukraine is going through a period of development. So, in 2017, there were 1569 fitness facilities, which is 150 more than in 2016, with 56% are fitness clubs, 10% are fitness studios, 9% each are martial arts clubs and Pilates studios 7% are women's fitness clubs, 3% – yoga studios, 3% – dance studios, 2% – swimming pools.

It should be noted that all objects carry out staffing with the use of various methods, strategies, provision of working conditions, personnel selection, advanced training of workers, which, in our opinion, requires systematization, coordination of approaches and critical analysis of the state of staffing.

Paying tribute to the developments of domestic and foreign scientists, it should be noted that the complex and multidimensional problem of staffing in the system of health fitness in Ukraine has not yet become the subject of a separate scientific study. The relevance of this issue is explained by the presence of such contradictions between:

- growing pace of development of the domestic fitness industry and the insufficient level of feasibility of its staffing system;
- formation in Ukraine of the national qualifications system and the lack of organizational and managerial foundations of this process in the system of recreational fitness;
- increasing the demands of consumers of fitness services and employers to the competence of fitness personnel and the lack of relevant professional standards in Ukraine;
- existing practice of improving the competence of specialists in health-improving fitness throughout the entire period of their professional activities and the uncertainty of the organizational and managerial conditions for the implementation of a modern system of continuous professional development of fitness personnel in Ukraine.

Conclusions / Discussion

Analysis of literary sources and information resources of the Internet, domestic and foreign practical experience shows that the strengthening of the social significance of the professional activities of fitness industry professionals is due to new socio-economic changes, the development of our state in accordance with the new market conditions. The processes of transformation, globalization and integration that are currently taking place in the system of health fitness in Ukraine require the improvement of its staffing.

The system analysis of published materials suggests that in recent years, both domestic and foreign scientists have increased their attention to personnel issues in the field of physical culture and sports, in particular, in the fitness industry. The necessity of providing the labor market with competitive specialists has been proved, since the professional environment discusses the problem of the lack of qualified fitness person-

nel and the mismatch of the competences of these personnel with modern challenges.

The need of a scientific substantiation of the concept of staffing in the system of fitness and fitness in Ukraine was updated to overcome the revealed contradictions between the existing practice and the requirements of modernity.

Discussion remains questions of the appropriateness and prospects of borrowing some elements, forms and methods of professional standards for fitness staff.

of organizing staffing the fitness industry in other countries; taking into account a number of methodological provisions: informative and in-depth study of existing experience, the result of which may be the improvement of the concept of personnel management of the fitness industry.

Prospects for further research lie in the analysis of the legal regulation of the organization of proper staffing of the modern fitness industry, as well as the development of pro-

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